

Coordination Compounds of Organometallic Bases of Group IV Elements. Part-IX

SURAJ P. NARULA*, RAVI SHANKAR and (Miss) NEETA KAPUR

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

The reactions of anilino/2-fluoroanilino/2,4-difluoroanilino/benzylamino/n-butylaminomethylbis(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)/tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)/tri-n-propoxysilanes in petroleum ether with SnCl_4 and TiCl_4 in the same solvent at -15 to -5° give solid compounds of composition $\text{R}_n\text{Si}(\text{NHR}')_{4-n}\cdot x\text{MCl}_4$, where $\text{R} = \text{CF}_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$, or CH_3 ; $\text{R}' = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{F}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{F}_2$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_3$, or $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$; $n = 0, 1$ or 2 ; $x = 1, 2$ or 3 ; and $\text{M} = \text{Sn}$ or Ti . These compounds have been characterised by elemental analyses, infrared and ^1H and ^{19}F nmr spectra as well as ligand exchange reactions. The novel feature of these reactions is the formation of compounds of tetrakis(organoamino)silanes on reaction with organoaminotris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silane with the Lewis acids.

THE reactions of benzylamino/anilino/n-butylamino-triorganoxy/tris(2-chloroethoxy)/(2-chloroethoxy)-alkoxy/alkylorganoxysilanes with antimony(III) halides and tin(IV) and titanium(IV) chlorides result in the isolation of adducts of the disproportionated aminosilanes. It is also observed that disproportionation of the aminosilanes takes place only if silicon atom carries organoxy group(s)^{1,2}. Presently, benzylamino/anilino/n-butylamino/2-fluoroanilino/2,4-difluoroanilinomethylbis(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)/tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)/tri-n-propoxysilanes have been reacted with tin(IV) and titanium(IV) chlorides with a view to ascertaining the role of fluoro-substituted groups on silicon atom of the aminosilanes in these types of reactions. The results obtained are reported herein.

Experimental

All operations were carried out under dry nitrogen atmosphere. The solvents used were dried by conventional methods. Titanium(IV) and tin(IV) chlorides (Reidel, Pure) were distilled before use.

Elemental analyses, infrared and ^1H nmr spectroscopic data were obtained as reported before³. ^1H and ^{19}F nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 containing a small amount of DMSO-d_6 using TMS as internal standard.

Ligands: Benzylamino/n-butylaminotris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silanes, benzylamino/anilino-methylbis(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silanes, 2-fluoroanilino/2,4-difluoroanilino-tri-n-propoxysilanes were synthesised by the reactions of the chlorosilanes with the corresponding amines. The purity of these compounds was checked by infrared and ^1H nmr spectral data.

Adducts: Addition of equimolar quantities of tin(IV) or titanium(IV) chloride in petroleum ether

to any of the bases, (benzylamino/n-butylaminotris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silanes, benzylamino/anilino-methylbis(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silanes, 2-fluoroanilino/2,4-difluoroanilino-tri-n-propoxysilanes), in the same solvent at -15 to -5° resulted in the precipitation of a solid product in each case. The adducts were washed, dried under reduced pressure and analysed (Table 1).

Ligand exchange reaction: An adduct (10 mmol) was added to ethylene diamine (25 mmol), molten 2-2'-dipyridyl (25 mmol) or pyridine (d_6) (25 mmol) in a round-bottomed flask fitted with reflux condenser, silica gel moisture guard tube and dry nitrogen inlet tube. The contents were kept at $35-40^\circ$ for 3-4 h, thereafter, dry carbon tetrachloride (5-10 ml) was added to the reaction mixture and the contents filtered.

Results and Discussion

The compounds isolated are white and orange to brick-red solids with SnCl_4 and TiCl_4 , respectively. The compounds are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents except DMSO. However, the complexes obtained from 2-fluoroanilino-tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silane are soluble in nitromethane and conductance of their millimolar solutions show them to be 1:1 electrolytes. The composition of all the adducts isolated have been found to be $\text{R}_n\text{Si}(\text{NHR}')_{4-n}\cdot x\text{MCl}_4$, where $\text{R} = \text{CF}_3\text{CH}_2\text{O}$, CH_3 and $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}$; $n = 0$ or 1 ; $x = 1, 2$ or 3 ; $\text{R}' = n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_3$, C_6H_5 , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{F}$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{F}_2$. Analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Infrared spectra: A comparison of the infrared spectra of the adducts and of the parent aminosilanes show that ν_{NH} modes undergo a negative spectral shift of the order of $240-120\text{ cm}^{-1}$, thereby

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE ADDUCTS OF ORGANOAMINO(2,2,2-TRIFLUOROETHOXY)ALKOXY/ALKYL-SILANES WITH TIN(IV) AND TITANIUM(IV) CHLORIDES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		Cl	Ti/Sn	Si	N
1.	(C ₆ H ₅ FNH),Si.3TiCl ₄	40.0 (41.1)	13.2 (13.8)	2.5 (2.6)	5.1 (5.4)
2.	(C ₆ H ₅ FNH),Si.3SnCl ₄	33.9 (34.1)	27.9 (28.3)	2.0 (2.2)	4.1 (4.4)
3.	(CF ₃ CH ₂ O)Si(NHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅),.2TiCl ₄	34.2 (34.4)	11.2 (11.6)	3.2 (3.4)	4.9 (5.1)
4.	(CF ₃ CH ₂ O)Si(NHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅),.2SnCl ₄	29.2 (29.4)	24.0 (24.4)	2.7 (2.9)	4.1 (4.3)
5.	(CF ₃ CH ₂ O)Si(NHC ₆ H ₅),.2TiCl ₄	39.0 (39.2)	12.9 (13.2)	3.5 (3.8)	5.8 (5.8)
6.	(CF ₃ CH ₂ O)Si(NHC ₆ H ₅),.2SnCl ₄	32.5 (32.8)	26.8 (27.3)	2.7 (3.2)	4.6 (4.8)
7.	CH ₃ Si(NHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅),.2TiCl ₄	38.0 (38.3)	12.4 (12.9)	3.5 (3.7)	5.3 (5.6)
8.	CH ₃ Si(NHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅),.2SnCl ₄	31.8 (32.2)	26.5 (26.7)	2.9 (3.1)	4.5 (4.7)
9.	CH ₃ Si(NHC ₆ H ₅),.2TiCl ₄	40.4 (40.6)	13.4 (13.7)	3.6 (4.0)	5.8 (6.0)
10.	CH ₃ Si(NHC ₆ H ₅),.2SnCl ₄	33.2 (33.8)	27.8 (28.0)	2.7 (3.3)	5.0 (5.5)
11.	(C ₆ H ₇ O),Si(NHC ₆ H ₄ F),.TiCl ₄	25.2 (25.5)	8.4 (8.6)	4.7 (5.0)	5.0 (5.0)
12.	(C ₆ H ₇ O),Si(NHC ₆ H ₄ F),.SnCl ₄	22.2 (22.6)	17.2 (17.3)	4.5 (4.6)	4.4 (4.6)
13.	(C ₆ H ₇ O),Si(NHC ₆ H ₄ F),.TiCl ₄	23.7 (23.9)	7.6 (8.1)	4.4 (4.7)	4.4 (4.7)
14.	(C ₆ H ₇ O),Si(NHC ₆ H ₄ F),.SnCl ₄	21.5 (21.4)	18.0 (17.9)	4.4 (4.2)	4.3 (4.2)

TABLE 2—¹H AND ¹⁹F nmr SPECTRAL DATA OF THE ADDUCTS OF ORGANOAMINO(2,2,2-TRIFLUOROETHOXY)-ALKOXY/ALKYLSILANES WITH TIN(IV) AND TITANIUM(IV) CHLORIDES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Chemical shift (δ)						
		OCH ₂	NCH ₂	O ₂ H ₂	CH ₂	CH ₃	CF ₃	C ₆ H ₄ F/C ₆ H ₄ F ₂
1.	(FC ₆ H ₄ NH),Si.3MCl ₄	—	—	7.3	—	—	—	127
2.	(CF ₃ CH ₂ O)Si(NHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅),.2MCl ₄	4.0	4.1	7.4	—	—	77.0	—
3.	(CF ₃ CH ₂ O)Si(NHCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂),.2MCl ₄	8.9	2.9	—	0.85	1.4	77.5	—
4.	CH ₃ Si(NHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅),.2MCl ₄	—	4.1	7.5	—	—	—	—
5.	CH ₃ Si(NHC ₆ H ₅),.2MCl ₄	—	—	7.3	0.3	—	—	—
6.	(CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ O),Si(NHC ₆ H ₄ F),.MCl ₄	8.8	—	7.4	0.9	1.6	—	127
7.	(CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂ O),Si(NHC ₆ H ₄ F),.MCl ₄	8.9	—	7.5	0.9	1.55	—	124 120

suggesting nitrogen atom to be the donor site. ν_{CO} and $\nu_{SiO(C)}$ bands are present at ~ 1660 and 1070 cm^{-1} , respectively, except in the case of adducts of benzylamino/anilinomethylbis(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy) and 2-fluoroanilino tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silanes wherein they are completely absent, thereby showing the absence of fluoroethoxy groups in these compounds. CF₃ modes are observed at 1260, 660 and 540 cm^{-1} except for the adducts of 2-fluoroanilino tris(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silane and benzylamino/anilinomethylbis(2,2,2-trifluoroethoxy)silanes. In the latter complexes, there is complete disproportionation of the base molecules giving corresponding tris/tetrakis(amino/anilino/fluoroanilino)silane adducts.

¹H nmr spectra : The spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ + DMSO-d₆. For the adducts of composition Si(NHC₆H₄F)₃.3MCl₄, only the base proton signals are observed. These are recorded in

Table 2. The Si-CH₃ protons are observed as a singlet at δ 0.3 and OCH₂ group protons are observed at δ 3.8-4.0, CH₂ and CH₃ of n-propoxy group appear at δ 0.9 and 1.4, respectively. The relative ratios of the protons through proton counts give the composition of the ligands in the adducts as given above. ¹⁹F nmr data (wherever applicable) also support the results (Table 2). The nature of the ligand has been further confirmed by subjecting these compounds to ligand exchange reactions with 2,2'-dipyridyl, ethylene diamine or pyridine (d₆). The liberated bases are characterised by infrared and ¹H and ¹⁹F nmr spectra.

From these observations we may infer that the substitution of fluorine in the alkoxy groups facilitates the disproportionation reactions, thereby leading to the isolation of tetrakis(2-fluoroanilino)silane adduct. On the other hand, (2-fluoroani-

lino)/(2,4-difluoroanilino)tri-n-propoxysilanes yield only bis(fluoroanilino)di-n-propoxysilane adducts.

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